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Understanding of Mass Transport Limitation in Near-Neutral Anion-Exchange-Membrane Water Electrolysis

Prattakorn Metem* (1), John G. Petrovick (1,2), Björn Eriksson (1),
Göran Lindbergh (1)

(1) Department of Chemical Engineering, KTH Royal Institute of Technology,
Stockholm/Sweden;

(2) COMSOL AB, Stockholm/Sweden;

*Contact corresponding authors: www.EFCF.com/ContactRequest

Abstract

Anion-exchange-membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE) is a nascent green hydrogen production technology which combines the advantages of proton-exchange-membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE) and alkaline water electrolysis (AWE). Using less-concentrated KOH feed is preferable and an active area of research. However, it is generally known that AEMWE's performance suffers greatly from using near-neutral pH feeds (e.g., pure water), which is attributed to kinetic losses and the poor conductivity of water. Mass-transport limitations are also observed in a low pH condition, which introduces another loss at high current density. However, mass transport in these systems has not been described extensively in the literature. To improve the understanding of mass transport phenomena in AEMWE *in-operando*, we have developed an asymmetric feed system to probe the impacts of KOH transport in the mass-transport-limited region. The cell is constructed using a membrane electrode assembly (MEA) fabricated by Pt/C catalyst coated directly on the membrane as the cathode and iridium oxide (IrO_x) sprayed on a stainless-steel porous transport layer (PTL) as the anode. PiperION is used as the anion exchange membrane. Cells constructed in this way are able to reach a high current density, even in pure water conditions, in which the mass transport limitation region is observed. Through combination with mathematical modeling, we have shown that, by utilizing various combinations of feeds, it is possible to elucidate the cause of mass transport limitations in different systems. As a result, this work paves a way for moving towards pure water electrolysis.

Introduction

Anion exchange membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE) is a newly emerged hydrogen production technology. Unlike proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE), AEMWE holds several advantages through its ability to use non-noble cheaper catalysts, e.g., nickel (Ni), instead of critical raw materials (CRMs) such as platinum (Pt) and iridium (Ir). This ability to use non-noble catalysts substantially lowers the capital costs of AEMWE. Furthermore, AEMWE can avoid the use of perfluorosulfonic acid (PFSA) polymer, which is highly environmentally toxic but is the state-of-the-art polymer for PEMWE [1]. Therefore, much research has been focusing on development of efficient AEMWE systems.

Figure 1. Schematic of an anion exchange membrane water electrolyzer (AEMWE).

A general schematic of an AEMWE is shown in Figure 1. AEMWE encompasses water splitting in basic media through equation 1 – 3. Equation 1 shows the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) occurring at the cathode, while the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) transpires at the anode. The generated hydroxide ions (OH⁻) from HER at the cathode are transported through the anion exchange membrane (AEM) to the anode and consumed during the OER to maintain charge neutrality.

Feeding both electrodes with basic electrolytes, generally 1 M potassium hydroxide (KOH), improves conductivity and kinetics of the system, resulting in improved performance. However, concentrated KOH is highly corrosive, and it has been shown that OH⁻ can degrade the membranes and the catalyst layers overtime [2]. Thus, this low stability of AEMWE is hindering its utilization on the industrial scale.

One way to maintain a similar performance while reducing the amount of KOH is to use asymmetric feed systems, where the two sides of AEMWE, *i.e.*, the cathode and the anode, are subjected to different conditions. One example of this system is the dry-cathode operation, in which the anolyte is generally fed with concentrated KOH (1 M), and the cathode is left dry. This system eliminates the use of KOH on one side, while providing the

benefit of easier gas separation and comparable performance with AEMWE system fed with 1 M KOH on both sides. Nevertheless, at high, industrial scale current density, the cell's water management becomes a major problem, where membrane dry-outs are observed [3].

Hence, feeding both sides with electrolytes while keeping one side as concentrated KOH can be beneficial to the AEMWE system. Furthermore, using near-neutral feeds for AEMWE often results in mass transport limitations observable in the polarization curve, which is rarely explored [4]. Herein, we extensively explore the idea of liquid-fed asymmetric feed systems. Through both *in-operando* and *ex-situ* tests, we have elucidated the possible cause of mass transport limitations of these systems, paving the way forwards in development of near-neutral feed AEMWE systems.

1. Scientific Approach

The experiments are separated into two parts: *ex-situ* and *in-operando* measurements, shown in Figure 2. In the *in-operando* measurements, a single-cell AEMWE was built, and the cell is fed with different permutation of feeds. A pH probe is inserted in-line with the effluent to observe the change in pH over time. The recorded polarization curves and pH changes were compared. Diffusivity of KOH was extracted using mathematical modeling.

Ex-situ measurements were done to examine the transport properties of the anion-exchange membrane when the membrane was exposed to different KOH concentrations using a H-cell. Through these two sets of experiments, we are able to elucidate the effect of using asymmetric feed conditions.

Figure 2. Schematic for a) *ex-situ* measurement, b) *in-operando* measurements, and c) feeding system. The anolyte and the catholyte are heated by the heat exchanger before feeding into the AEMWE cell. pH meter is connected in-line with the effluent to record the change in pH over different operating conditions.

2. Experiments/Calculations/Simulations

Membrane electrode assembly fabrication

Platinum on carbon (Pt/C) catalyst coated membrane (CCM) is used as the cathode catalyst in all *in-operando* experiments. The spray-coating procedure is reported previously by our group [5]. Briefly, Pt/C catalyst powder (40% weight Pt, Tanaka, Japan) was suspended in DI water. PiperION ionomer (Versogen, USA, IEC = 2.3), was dissolved in ethanol. Isopropanol was then added later to the ionomer solution. The ethanol/isopropanol-ionomer solution was then added drop-by-drop to the catalyst suspension. The final ink had a composition of 10% weight-to-volume total solid content, 75% volume isopropanol, 20% water, and 5% ethanol. The ink was ultrasonicated and sprayed onto PiperION membrane by ultrasonic spray coater (ExactaCoat, Sono-Tek). The final loading was 0.45 mg-Pt cm⁻².

Iridium oxide (IrO_x) catalyst coated substrate (CCS) is used as the anode in most *in-operando* measurements to investigate the performance at a higher current density. The IrO_x catalyst layer is hand-sprayed using an airbrush. A similar procedure has been reported previously in literature [6]. Firstly, PiperION ionomer was dissolved in ethanol, and was mixed with isopropanol, while IrO_x catalysts (Tanaka, Japan) were suspended in DI water. The ethanol/isopropanol-ionomer solution was added to IrO_x catalysts, and the final composition is 5% weight-to-volume total solid content, 75% volume isopropanol, 20% water, and 5% ethanol. The ink was ultrasonicated and tip sonicated before loaded onto the airbrush. The ink was sprayed on stainless steel cloth (316-type, SF200.05, Forsbergs Metallduk, Sweden), and the resulting catalyst layer had a loading of 1.33 mg-IrO_x cm⁻². To improve the adhesion of the CCS to the membrane, an additional 1 mg-ionomer cm⁻² was deposited on the produced CCS.

In-operando measurements and electrochemical characterization

The cell components are shown in Figure 2b. The active area was 1 cm². Stainless steel cloth was used as the cathode porous transport layer (PTL). A nickel felt or the IrO_x-coated stainless steel cloth were used as the anode, and are named Ni-anode cell, and IrO_x-anode cell, respectively. The Pt/C-coated membrane was inserted in between the cathode PTL and the anode to create a membrane electrode assembly (MEA). The MEA was then inserted between the flow fields, and the cell was sealed with polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) gaskets.

Anolyte and catholyte were heated in a heat exchanger before feeding into the AEMWE cell, as shown in Figure 2c, and both electrolytes were not recycled back into their respective reservoirs. The polarization curve was recorded with constant current steps for the Ni-anode cell and potential steps for the IrO_x-anode cell. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was recorded at 0.5 A cm⁻² or at 1.6 V for the two cases, respectively. A pH probe was used to record pH of the effluent over time, and the pH response at different operational states were determined. The pH profile, Nernst-Planck equation, and mass balance can be used to approximate the diffusivity of KOH [7].

Ex-situ membrane characterization

Diffusivity of KOH are also determined via *ex-situ* measurements (Figure 2a). The membrane was ion exchanged in 1 M KOH overnight before the experiment. The membrane was then inserted between two reservoirs of an h-cell. One side of the h-cell was filled with water, while the other reservoir was filled with 0.5 M, 1 M, 2 M, or 3 M KOH. Meanwhile, pH was recorded overtime using a pH probe inserted into the water reservoir. The pH profile was used to calculate the concentration of KOH, which was later used for determination of diffusivities at different starting concentrations using Fick's law and pressure-driven water transport [7, 8].

3. Results

Figure 3. a) Polarization curves of Ni-anode cells fed with different permutations of electrolytes. Cell performances can be grouped into three groups: (1) the high pH anolyte, (2) the high pH catholyte, and (3) the near-neutral anolyte and catholyte. b) Post-mortem Ni felts removed from the Water(a)/1M(c) and the Water(a)/Water(c) cells compared with the pristine. c) Polarization curves of IrO_x-anode cell with stainless steel (SS) as cathode PTL fed with different anolyte, while catholyte was kept at 1 M KOH. d) Polarization curve of the IrO_x-anode cell with carbon as cathode PTL fed with water catholyte and 1 M KOH catholyte along with pH at different operating current densities. e) KOH diffusivities (D_{KOH}) at different average concentrations between the two sides of the membrane calculated from *ex-situ* and *in-operando* results normalized by D_{KOH} of the *ex-situ* measurement at the average concentration of 0.05 M.

The Ni-anode cells were fed with different permutations of electrolytes (1 M KOH anolyte and 1 M KOH catholyte (1M(a)/1M(c)), 1M(a)/Water(c), Water(a)/1M(a), 1mM(a)/1mM(c), and Water(a)/Water(c)), and the polarization curves are shown in Figure 3a. The performance of the cell can clearly be grouped into three groups, which are the high pH anolyte group (1M(a)/1M(c)), the high pH catholyte group (Water(a)/1M(c)), and the near-neutral pH group (1mM(a)/1mM(c), and Water(a)/Water(c)).

There are two key observations based on the polarization curves. Firstly, the performance of the 1M(a)/Water cell is similar to 1M(a)/1M(c), even though the kinetics of HER should drastically drop in pure water. For instance, it has been reported that exchange current density drops by approximately 30% when the pH surrounding the catalyst changes from pH 14 to pH 13 [9]. Here, the 1M(a)/Water performs much better than expected as there is only approximately 200 mV increase at 1 A cm⁻² compared to the 1M(a)/1M(c) cell.

Secondly, Water(a)/1M(c) cell also performs better than expected. It is well-known that OER kinetics are heavily reliant on environmental pH, which is reportedly halved when the pH reduces from 14 to 13 [9]. As such, the Water(a)/1M(c) cell should perform similar to the near-neutral pH group, instead of the high catholyte case.

Based on these results, we hypothesize that KOH likely crosses over from the more concentrated side to the less concentrated side. This KOH crossover implies that the local pH on the less concentrated feed is much higher than the influent pH. This would explain the better-than-expected performance observed for both 1M(a)/Water(c) and Water(a)/1M(c) cases.

To substantiate this hypothesis, the utilized Ni felts were removed from the Water(a)/Water(c) and the Water(a)/1M(c) cells after recording polarization curve, shown in Figure 3b. Here, the Ni felt removed from the Water(a)/Water(c) cell shows a significant corrosion, as the black oxides can be readily observed by eye, in contrast to Ni felt removed from the Water(a)/1M(c) cell where almost no black oxides can be observed. As Ni is corroded below pH 9, this result suggests that the anodic local pH is higher for the Water(a)/1M(c) than Water(a)/Water(c) case, thus supporting the idea of KOH crossover.

To further investigate the impact of crossover at higher current density, the IrO_x-anode cell was used to conduct further experiments. Here, the cathode was kept at 1 M KOH, while the anolyte concentration varied (1 M, 0.1 M, 10 mM, 1 mM, Water). The performance of each cell is shown in Figure 3c. Here, it can clearly be seen that mass transport limitation starts occurring when the anolyte concentration is below 10 mM, suggesting that the availability of OH⁻ is dominated by the solution pH. Further, at low feed concentrations the KOH crossover becomes the main source of OH⁻ and directly limits the maximum current.

To reach an even higher current density, the IrO_x-anode cell with a better performance was constructed by substituting the stainless steel porous transport layer on the cathode with a carbon porous transport layer (Sigracet 22BB) which provided better contact. The pH meter is connected in-line with the anode effluent, and both the polarization curve and pH profile are shown in Figure 3d. A current density of more than 2 A cm⁻² can be reached at 2.5 V, and the mass transport limitation is observed at around the current density of 1.25 A cm⁻². The pH profile also has a similar behavior where the pH reaches the highest at the same current density and starts to slightly decrease afterwards. This suggests that there is a correlation between anodic pH and mass transport limitation. Since the concentration difference between the two sides also influences the mass transport limitation (Figure 3c), it is likely that the membrane properties, such as diffusivity of KOH, change with the concentration difference between the two sides.

Ex-situ measurements were conducted to observe the change in membrane diffusivity in different concentration differences of the two sides, *i.e.*, in different concentration gradients. pH change over time is used to approximate the diffusivity of KOH under different concentration gradients, and the results are shown in Figure 3e, along with diffusivities calculated from the *in-operando* measurements using recorded pH and the Nernst-Planck equation. It can clearly be seen that the KOH diffusivity through the membrane varies with its environment, up to 15 times compared between the average starting concentration of 0.05 M and 1 M. Meanwhile, the diffusivity calculated from *in-operando* tests also show a drastic increase when the concentration gradient increases. This emphasizes the importance of using the correct diffusivity to gauge the magnitude of KOH crossover. Moreover, as mobility and diffusivity are linked, the lower diffusivity signifies that mobility decreases [7]. As such, this decreases in diffusivity at lower concentration gradient may relate to the observed mass transport limitation at these low concentration gradients.

To conclude, we have hypothesized that KOH crosses over from the more concentrated side to the less concentrated side, resulting in a higher local pH and a better performance. When the anode is fed with lower concentrations, mass transport limitation is observed,

which is supported by the lower effluent pH. We propose that it is likely due to the change in membrane properties such as KOH diffusivity at different concentration gradients, which we have proved in both the *ex-situ* tests and calculations from the *in-operando* measurements. This emphasizes the need to further study AEMWE systems under asymmetric feeds to understand and develop near-neutral electrolyte AEMWE systems.

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